

Machine learning based meta-analysis using multiple toxicogenomics datasets does not improve genotoxicity prediction

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Abstract

Toxicogenomics-based approaches using in vitro cell models, developed as alternatives to animal testing, have been shown to be able to predict genotoxicity in vivo with accuracies above 85%, thereby outperforming the standard test batteries required by regulatory agencies. Despite their performance these approaches are not widely used yet due to the limited number of compounds used, the imbalance in classes, and/or the type of cell model used. In this study, we aim to overcome these hurdles by performing a meta-analysis on the large amounts of toxicogenomics data sets that have been generated the past decade, thereby further improving in vivo genotoxicity prediction. From the diXa Data Warehouse, ArrayExpress, GEO and Open TG-GATEs we collected gene expression data for human, rat and mouse in vitro liver cell models exposed to 156, 88 and 44 compounds with known genotoxicity information, respectively, at different time points and dosages resulting in 853, 702 and 100 experiments, respectively. The obtained datasets were merged and pre-processed per species. Species specific prediction models were built by using 10 machine learning algorithms on 10 train/test sets, each containing 80% of the data for training and 20% for testing. To avoid bias and possibly overfitting experiments using the same compound were all placed in either the training or test set. Support Vector Machines algorithm had the best accuracy for predicting genotoxicity in vivo at 69-82% with 81-93% specificity and 46-61% sensitivity. In conclusion, the meta-analysis did not improve in vivo genotoxicity prediction.